

EFFECT OF ETHNOSCIENCE STRATEGY ON CREATIVE-THINKING SKILLS OF STUDENTS WITH DIFFERENT COGNITIVE STYLES IN BASIC SCIENCE

¹Bridget Cosmas Ogbilikwe, ²Jackson Ochigbudu Ode, ³Msuur Tofi and ⁴Tine Agenor

Department of Science and Mathematics Education, Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi

E-mail: odejackson90@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18233943>

Keywords:

Ethnoscience, creative thinking skills, Basic Science and cognitive styles

ABSTRACT: *This study ascertained the effect of ethnoscience strategy on creative thinking skills of Basic 8 students with different cognitive styles in Benue State using pretest-posttest quasi-experimental control group design. The population of the study was 1,650 Basic 8 students from the 19 Upper Basic Schools in Otukpo, Benue State. The sample size for the study consist of 70 students from two sampled schools within the study area obtained through multi-stage sampling procedure. The instrument used for data collection was Torrance test of Creative thinking (TTCT) adapted to identify students' level of creative thinking skills. The reliability of TTCT was established using Spearman rank correlation and it yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.89. The data obtained were analyzed using mean and standard Deviation to answer research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of confidence. Findings revealed that there was a significant difference in the mean creative thinking scores of impulsive Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using the ethnoscience strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching strategy; there was a significant difference in the mean creative thinking scores of reflective Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using the ethnoscience strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching strategy and there was a significant difference between the mean creative thinking skills of impulsive and reflective Basic 8 students taught using the Ethnoscience strategy. Based on the findings, it is recommended that Basic Science teachers should use ethnoscience strategy to enhance students' creative thinking skills in the subject.*

Introduction

Bridget Cosmas Ogbilikwe, Jackson Ochigbudu Ode, Msuur Tofi and Tine Agenor

Science education today plays a key role in improving the scientific literacy and developing scientific attitude of citizens of any nation. According to Ode, Akpoghol, and Aondover (2020), the teaching-learning process is undergoing transformation with the advent of science and inventions, especially in the field of science education. De La Cruz (2022) opined that the study of science helps children cultivate a sense of curiosity, objectivity, honesty, and critical thinking and the author confirms the fact that students generally have high perceptions of innovativeness in the aspect of science. Science subjects are designed to expose students to scientific skills, which can help them resolve day-to-day problems. According to the author, there are several science subjects at secondary and basic education levels in Nigeria such as Chemistry, Physics, Biology, Mathematics, Agricultural Science and Basic Science.

Basic Science is a science subject that present science in a unified or holistic form with the intent of building scientifically literate citizens that can rationalize and engage scientific skills and attitudes in solving real life daily problems (Chima, 2021). Basic Science is seen as the foundation of science and technology-related subjects for many fields of learning such as medicine, forestry, agriculture, biotechnology, Engineering, and nursing, and has contributed immensely to the scientific and technological growth of a nation such as Nigeria. The study of Basic Science equips students with useful skills, concepts, principles and theories that will enable them face the challenges of science subjects in the future. In this regard, Nofzinger (2022) affirms that students' access to advanced science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) courses and careers and their ability to be critical thinkers and engaged

citizens depend on their participation in science education.

The Basic Science curriculum is expected to enable the learners; develop interest in science and technology; acquire basic knowledge in science and technology; apply scientific and technological knowledge and skill to meet contemporary societal needs; it is also expected to help the students take advantage of the numerous career opportunities provided by science and technology; become prepared for further studies in science and technology, avoid drug abuse and related vices; and be safety and security conscious (FGN,2014).

In spite of the numerous importance of Basic Science, the teaching and learning of the subject is facing some challenges. From 2018 to 2023 there has been low and inconsistent students' performance in the subject due to poor creative thinking skills. For instance, the results analysis of Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) in Basic Science for the 2018/2019 academic session showed students that passed at credit to be 63.8% which is above average performance. However, in 2019/2020, the result showed a decrease in those that passed at credit level performance to 59.90%. In 2020/2021, there was a slight increase in the percentage of those that passed which was 63.58. In 2021/2022, result showed 60% of students passed. Again in 2022/2023 however, there was decrease with the percentage score of those that passed at credit level which was 57.70%. This shows that there is an oscillatory movement and therefore indicates inconsistency in students' performance in Basic Science. This inconsistent trend in performance according to (Ode & Eriba, 2020), has been attributed to the use of ineffective conventional teaching strategies which according to Awwiri (2017) leads to students' low creative thinking

skills which could further lead to limited problem solving abilities in students. The traditional chalk and talk teaching strategies are not capable of helping students understand the taught concepts for improved academic performance and engaging them actively to sharpen their creative thinking skills. Meaningful teaching and learning of Basic Science is expected to provide a nexus between students' real-life experiences and learning experiences. This could help the learners to better understand the relevance of science to their lives and their environment. One of such inquiry based strategy is Ethnoscience.

Ethnoscience strategy is a teaching strategy that involves the study and application of indigenous knowledge systems that represent local understandings of nature, often passed down orally and through practice. It is an essential form of cognitive mapping by indigenous cultures to interact with their environment Semali and Kincheloe (2022). Similarly, Agrawal (2021) defines Ethnoscience as a body of knowledge that encompasses the classifications, beliefs, and practices of indigenous communities regarding natural phenomena, developed over generations and deeply embedded in cultural contexts. Nabhan (2023) points out that Ethnoscience highlights how local people engage in scientific thinking, observation, hypothesis, and experimentation which are rooted in cultural heritage and adapted to specific ecosystems. Ethnoscience therefore is a teaching strategy that integrates indigenous knowledge and cultural practices into science education to make learning relevant and meaningful for students from diverse cultural backgrounds.

Ethnoscience strategy allows students to connect their personal and communal knowledge bases with scientific concepts,

fostering a more holistic understanding of science. By comparing and contrasting their beliefs, values, and experiences with modern scientific ideas, students can achieve a deeper comprehension and appreciation of science. A teacher who uses Ethnoscience strategy for teaching consciously develops and builds confidence and trust in the learner especially in the act of learning from their local environment. This strategy does not only makes science more accessible but also more relevant to students' lives, encouraging a more engaged and enthusiastic approach to learning. A teacher achieves this by creating a democratic teaching-learning environment where learners show no trace or sign of fear, intimidation, or any other symptom that can prevent them from demonstrating their creative manipulative skills and creative thinking abilities in the classroom (Douglas & Iyalagha, 2024).

Creative thinking is one aspect of skill and knowledge acquisition that has been described as key and fundamental in the twenty-first century. Creative thinking has been identified to be at the center of human survival and human flourishing, particularly in the twenty first century. Creative thinking according to Nasriati, Tahmir and Upu (2024) it is the ability to generate new and original ideas. Creative thinking is the process of seeking to perceive, discover the laws of things, consciously find new things to better understand the nature of things and phenomena as well as finding the cause and preventing them, eliminate the unsuitable and developing the good. It is the very definition of thinking outside the box (the ability to approach problems or tasks with innovative, unconventional, or creative ideas that may not be immediately apparent or within the scope of traditional methods or thinking patterns) by students irrespective of their cognitive styles

Cognitive styles describe how an individual acquires knowledge and how an individual processes information. According to Ufomadu and Okoli (2019), cognitive style is a person's characteristic mode of perceiving, thinking, remembering, and problem solving. It is a manner in which individuals perceive information in the environment and the patterns of thought that they use to develop a knowledge base about the world around them. Cognitive styles are related to mental behaviors, habitually applied by an individual to problem solving, and generally to way the information is obtained, sorted and utilized. This difference offers a robust framework for comparative analysis of cognitive performance. Furthermore, studying these styles provides valuable insights into broader cognitive and behavioural traits which includes attention control, metacognitive awareness and self-regulation which helps to ascertain student's decision making process and investigate how this cognitive style affect their choices. This study focused on impulsive and reflective cognitive styles.

Impulsive cognitive style is a learning style characterized by an individual's tendency to make quick decisions and act on them without giving much thought to the potential consequences or outcomes. Impulsive learners prioritize speed over accuracy and they act before fully analyzing all available information. This style can have both strengths and weaknesses, depending on the context and the individual's goals. Reflective cognitive style is a learning style where the learner carefully analyzes information before responding. It is a crucial aspect of the learning process, as it enables individuals to think deeply about their experiences and gain insights that can improve their understanding and creative thinking skills.

Though studies on Ethnoscience strategy are replete in literature, such research evidence was scarce in the study area in Basic Science to the best of the researchers' knowledge particularly with respect to the effect of the teaching strategy on students' creative thinking skills. It was against this background that this study ascertain the effect of Ethnoscience on creative thinking skills students with different cognitive styles in Basic Science in Benue State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of Ethnoscience Strategy on creative thinking skills of Basic 8 students with different cognitive styles in Benue State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the creative thinking skills of impulsive Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy and those taught using conventional teaching strategy.
2. Determine the creative thinking skills of reflective Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy and those taught using conventional teaching strategy.
3. Ascertain the difference in creative thinking skills between impulsive and reflective Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the difference in the creative thinking skills of impulsive Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy and those taught using conventional teaching strategy?
2. What is the difference in the mean creative thinking skills of reflective Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy and those taught conventional teaching strategy?

3. What is the difference in the mean creative thinking skills between impulsive and reflective Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean creative thinking scores of impulsive Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy and those taught using conventional teaching strategy.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean creative thinking scores of reflective Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy and those taught using conventional teaching strategy.

3. There is no significant difference in the mean creative thinking skills of impulsive and reflective Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy

Research Method

This study adopted the quasi experimental design because it examines the relationship between cause and effect. It employed a Pretest posttest quasi-experimental control group design. The choice of this design is due to the fact that the study used intact classes since it is not feasible to adopt true experimental design as it will distort the academic programme of the schools involved. The population of the study was 1,650 Basic 8 students from the 19 Upper Basic Schools in Otukpo. (State Universal Basic Education Board, 2023). The sample size for the study consist of 70 students from two sampled schools within the study area through multi-stage sampling procedure. The instrument used for data collection was Torrance test of Creative thinking (TTCT) adapted to identify students' level of creative thinking skills. The instrument had sections A and B. Section a sought bio-data

information such as name of school. Section B sought information on creative thinking skills of students. TTCT was made up of three activities that test the creative thinking skills of students. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from science education and one from Measurement and Evaluation, all from the faculty of education, Rev. Fr, Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. In a bid to ascertain the reliability of TTCT the researchers conducted a trial test with 30 students from school which is not part of the main study in Otukpo but has similar characteristics as the sample for the study. The reliability of TTCT was established using Spearman rank correlation and it yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.89. Pretest was administered to the students before treatment and data were retrieved after the test. The treatment lasted for six weeks after which posttest was administered to both groups. The experimental group was taught using the Ethnoscience Strategy. Ethnoscience Strategy as used in this study involves instructing the students practically on culturally loaded activities on the topic chemicals of Basic-8 curriculum. The control group was taught Basic Science concepts using conventional chalk and talk Strategy.

The data obtained were analyzed using mean and standard Deviation to answer research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of confidence. The choice of ANCOVA is to remove the initial difference between groups since study involves pretesting of subjects since intact classes was used. The decision rule in the null hypothesis was that if the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis will be rejected, but if the p-value is not less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected.

Results

Research Question One: What is the difference in the creative thinking skills of impulsive Basic 8 students taught Basic Science

using Ethnoscience strategy and those taught using conventional teaching strategy?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on Creative Thinking Skills of Impulsive Students based on Teaching Method

Method	Sample (n)	Pre-TTCT		Post- TTCT		Gain
		Mean	St. D.	Mean	St. D.	
Ethnoscience Strategy	21	24.90	6.29	64.38	7.54	39.48
Conventional Teaching Strategy	17	24.53	4.96	44.88	6.67	20.35
Mean Difference		0.37		19.5		19.13

Table 1 presents the mean and standard deviation scores of impulsive Basic 8 students' creative thinking skills before and after being taught Basic Science using two instructional methods: Ethnoscience strategy had mean scores of 24.90 with standard deviation of 6.29 in the Pre-CT and mean of 64.38 with standard deviation of 7.54 in the post-CT. While the Conventional teaching strategy had mean scores of 24.53 and 44.88 with standard deviations of 4.96 and 6.67 in the pre-CT and Post-CT respectively. Table 1 also, shows mean gain score of 39.48 for Ethnoscience strategy and mean

gain score of 20.35 for Conventional strategy with a mean gain difference of 19.13 in favour of Ethnoscience strategy. This implies that the impulsive students who were taught in the Ethnoscience students develop creative thinking skills more than those who were taught using conventional strategy.

Research Question Two: What is the difference in the creative thinking skills of reflective Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy and those taught conventional teaching strategy?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Creative Thinking Skills of Reflective Students based on Teaching Method

Method	Sample (n)	Pre-TTCT		Post- TTCT		Gain
		Mean	ST. D.	Mean	ST. D.	
Ethnoscience Strategy	18	26.56	6.60	66.61	6.49	40.05
Conventional Teaching Strategy	14	28.86	7.39	44.50	1.78	15.64
Mean Difference		2.3		22.11		24.41

Table 2 presents the mean and standard deviation scores of reflective Basic 8 students' creative thinking skills before and after being taught Basic Science using two instructional methods: Ethnoscience strategy had mean scores of 26.56 with standard deviation of 6.60 in the Pre-CT and mean of 66.61 with standard deviation of 6.49 in the post-CT. While the Conventional teaching strategy had mean scores of 28.86 and 44.50 with standard deviations of 7.39 and 1.78 in the pre-CT and Post-CT respectively. Table 3 further shows mean gain score of 40.05 for Ethnoscience strategy and

mean gain score of 15.64 for Conventional strategy with a mean gain difference of 24.41 in favour of Ethnoscience strategy. This implies that reflective students who were taught in the Ethnoscience students develop creative thinking skills more than those who were taught using conventional strategy.

Research Question Three: What is the difference in the mean creative thinking skills between impulsive and reflective Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of creative thinking skills between impulsive and reflective Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy

Cognitive Skills	Sample (n)	Pre-TTCT		Post- TTCT		Gain
		Mean	St. D.	Mean	St. D.	
Impulsive	21	23.38	4.70	69.29	1.93	45.91
Reflective	18	26.28	6.20	66.39	6.27	40.11
Mean Difference		2.9		2.9		5.8

Table 3 presents the mean and standard deviation scores between impulsive and reflective Basic 8 students’ creative thinking skills before and after being taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy: Impulsive students had mean scores of 23.38 with standard deviation of 4.70 in the Pre-CT and mean score of 69.29 with standard deviation of 1.93 in the post-CT. While the Reflective students had mean scores of 26.28 and 66.39 with standard deviations of 6.20 and 6.27 in the pre-CT and Post-CT respectively. Table 5 also shows mean gain score of 45.91 for Impulsive students and

mean gain score of 40.11 for Reflective students with a mean gain difference of 5.8 in favour of Reflective. This implies that impulsive students who were taught using Ethnoscience strategy develop creative thinking skills more than their counterpart reflective students.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the mean creative thinking scores of impulsive Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy and those taught using conventional teaching strategy.

Table 4: ANCOVA Summary of Creative Thinking Scores of Impulsive Basic 8 Students Taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience Strategy and Those Taught using Conventional Teaching Strategy.

Source	Type III Sum df of Squares		Mean Square F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	3572.021 ^a	2	1786.010	33.816	.000	.659
Intercept	5447.471	1	5447.471	103.142	.000	.747
PretCTImp	.185	1	.185	.004	.953	.000
StrategyImp	3566.138	1	3566.138	67.521	.000	.659
Error	1848.532	35	52.815			
Total	123137.000	38				
Corrected Total	5420.553	37				

a. R Squared = .659 (Adjusted R Squared = .639)

Table 4 shows ANCOVA result of $F(1, 35) = 67.521$; $p = 0.001 < 0.05$. Since $p < 0.05$ of the

probability alpha level, it implies that there is a significant difference in the mean creative

thinking scores of impulsive Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using the Ethnoscience strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching strategy. Students exposed to the Ethnoscience strategy performed significantly better in creative thinking than their counterparts taught with the conventional method. The Partial Eta Squared of 0.659

Table 5: ANCOVA Summary of Creative Thinking Scores of Reflective Basic 8 Students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience Strategy and those taught using Conventional Teaching Strategy.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	3910.470 ^a	2	1955.235	65.825	.000	.819
Intercept	4438.183	1	4438.183	149.416	.000	.837
PreCTRefl	60.373	1	60.373	2.033	.165	.065
StrategyRef	3903.098	1	3903.098	131.401	.000	.819
Error	861.405	29	29.704			
Total	108512.000	32				
Corrected Total	4771.875	31				

a. R Squared = .819 (Adjusted R Squared = .807)

Table 5 shows ANCOVA result of $F(1, 29) = 131.401$ $p = 0.001 < 0.05$. Since $p < 0.05$ of the probability alpha level, it implies that there is a significant difference in the mean creative thinking scores of reflective Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using the Ethnoscience strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching strategy. Reflective students exposed to the Ethnoscience strategy performed significantly better in creative thinking than

indicates that that effect size of 65.9% account for the difference in performance between the two teaching strategies.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the mean creative thinking scores of reflective Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy and those taught using conventional teaching strategy.

their counterparts taught with the conventional method. The Partial Eta Squared of 0.819 indicates that that effect size of 81.9.0% accounts for the difference between the two teaching strategies.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference between the mean creative thinking skills of impulsive and reflective Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using Ethnoscience strategy.

Table 6: ANCOVA Summary of Creative Thinking Skills of Impulsive and Reflective Basic 8 Students taught Basic Science Using Ethnoscience Strategy.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	170.137 ^a	2	85.068	4.684	.016	.207 ^a
Intercept	6268.598	1	6268.598	345.187	.000	.906
PreCTestImpandRefle	88.803	1	88.803	4.890	.033	.120
EthnoCognitiveStyle	124.979	1	124.979	6.882	.013	.160
Error	653.761	36	18.160			
Total	180888.000	39				
Corrected Total	823.897	38				

a. R Squared = .207 (Adjusted R Squared = .162)

The ANCOVA result in Table 6 (F (1, 36) = 6.882, p < 0.05, η² = 0.160) shows that cognitive style had a significant effect on students' creative thinking skills after controlling for pretest scores. This implies that the Ethnoscience strategy benefited impulsive and reflective learners differently. Therefore, Hypothesis Five, which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean creative thinking skills of impulsive and reflective Basic 8 students taught using the Ethnoscience strategy, is rejected. The Partial Eta Squared of 0.160 indicates that that effect size of 16.0% account for the difference in creative thinking skills between the cognitive styles.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of this study revealed a significant difference in the mean creative thinking scores of impulsive Basic 8 students taught Basic Science using the Ethnoscience strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching strategy. This could be due to the fact that students taught Basic Science using

Ethnoscience strategy is a context-based approach that connects scientific contents and real world contexts to promote students motivation and performance in science. It help students understand the importance of studying science and to develop a positive attitude towards science. Ethno-science teaching approach as a context-based approach to teaching science enables students to develop connection with science as they relate scientific concepts to their natural environment. This finding agrees with Verawati et al. (2022) and Dika et al. (2020) who found that in relation to improving CT performance, teaching practice with inquiry-creative learning integrated with Ethnoscience is most effective in improving the CT skills of students. The agreement of these findings suggests that ethnoscience teaching strategy fosters creative thinking among students since it connect science to the cultural context of the learners.

The findings shows that there is a significant difference in the mean creative thinking scores of reflective Basic 8 students taught Basic

Science using the Ethnoscience strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching strategy. The finding is also consistent with Dika et al. (2020) who found that Ethnoscience-based worksheets increase student creativity and are feasible to be used as teaching material. The study's finding aligned with Ayua et al. (2022) that findings showed a significant difference in the creative thinking level among different-ability students taught Basic Science using Lecture Method and those taught using creative teaching strategy. The agreement of this findings could be attributed to the fact that Ethnoscience teaching strategy is a strategy that integrates indigenous knowledge systems including traditional beliefs, practices, values and scientific understanding of local communities into formal science education. It emphasizes contextual learning where students relates scientific concepts to their cultural environment, language and daily experiences which in turn enhance students' creative thinking.

The result reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean creative thinking skills of impulsive and reflective Basic 8 students taught using the Ethnoscience strategy. This finding is not consistent with that of Nwankwo and Ure, (2021) whose results showed that there is a significant difference in the mean learning outcomes of students taught using ethno-science instructional strategy regardless of their cognitive styles. The study's finding is consistent with Fasasi et al. (2017) whose results showed that there was a significant main effect of Ethnoscience Instruction (EI) on learning outcomes in science and that Ethnoscience instruction is effective in promoting learners' creative thinking in science recommended it as an instructional method for learners especially in traditional communities. The application of

ethno-science learning approach is very vital in improving students' scientific literacy skills. Students can achieve science process skills more easily if teachers use ethno-science approach. In the field of science and Basic Science, ethno-science can be a solution to overcome the problem of students' low scientific literacy skills because it is a strategy encompasses learning experiences that integrate the culture in the learning experiences and educational process. The active engagement in the learning processes could stimulate curiosity that will engender critical thinking among students.

Conclusion

The findings have shown that Ethnoscience strategy enhanced students' creative thinking in Basic Science at the Upper-Basic School levels in Nigeria. Therefore, usage of the conventional strategy in teaching and learning Basic Science should be discouraged. Hence, adoption of Ethnoscience is appropriate for the teaching and learning of Basic Science and provide a way out for overcoming deficiency in developing students' creative thinking at the Upper-Basic School level. Ethnoscience strategy is also effective in enhancing students' creative thinking skills regardless of whether they have impulsive or reflective cognitive styles.

Recommendations

1. Based on findings of the present study, the following recommendations are outlined:
2. Basic Science teachers should use Ethnoscience strategy to enhance students' creative thinking skills in the subject.
3. Workshops should be frequently organized by educational bodies to sensitize Basic Science teachers on the use of Ethnoscience strategy for improving creative thinking skills of the students in the subject.
4. Authors of Upper-Basic school Basic Science textbooks should carefully include in the

teachers' guide illustrations within the local environment that supports the use Ethnoscience

References

Agrawal, A. (2021). Indigenous knowledge and the politics of classification. *International Journal of Indigenous Studies*, 45(2), 122–135.

Avwiri, E. (2017). Creativity of secondary school students: Entrepreneurial skills acquisition in the construction of potentiometer in Physics. *International Journal of Science and Technology (STECH) Bahir Dar-Ethiopia* 6(2), 61-75.

Ayua, G.A., Terhemba, W.K., & Ikyernum, G.S., (2022). Effect of Creative Teaching on Creative Thinking among Different-Ability Upper-Basic Science Students in Gboko-Town. *African Journal of Science Technology and Mathematics Education*, 8 (2), 182-188.

Basic Education Certificate Examination. (2019-2023). *Benue State Examination Board*. United States: State Government Press.

Chima, T. S. (2021). Basic Science Curriculum and Development In Nigeria: Post Coid-19 Challenges and Prospects. Unizik. *Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies* 7, 100-114.

De La Cruz, R. J. D. (2022). Science education in the Philippines. Singapore: *Springer Nature Singapore*, 331-345.

Dika, T., Abdul, G., Andi, U., & Hafnati, R. (2020). Ethnoscience –based student worksheet development to improve senior high school student creativity. *Journal Penelitian Pendidikan* 7(1), 26 -457.

strategy in the classroom to improve students' creative thinking skills.

Douglas, O., N., & Iyalagha, E. (2024). Teaching creative thinking skills in educational institutions in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Review*, 11 (4), 363-381.

Fasasi, R., A. (2017). Effects of Ethnoscience instruction, school location and parental educational status on learners' attitude towards science. *International Journal of Science Education*, 39(5), 548-564.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). *The National Policy on Education (Revised)*. Abuja: Federal Ministry of Education.

Nabhan, G. P. (2023). *Ethnobiology for the future: Linking cultural and ecological diversity*. University of Arizona Press.

Nofzinger, A. (2022). Teacher self-efficacy and science beliefs with the implementation of the ngss into a high school science curriculum. (Doctoral dissertation, Northeastern University).

Nwankwo, G. U. & Ure, I. (2021). Effects of ethno-science instructional strategy on junior secondary school students' achievement in basic science. *African Journal of Science, Technology & Mathematics Education*, 6(1), 2251-0141.

Ode J. O., Akpoghol T., V. & Aondover, A. (2020). Effect of kinesthetic and visual learning styles on Basic Science Students' Performance in Buruku Local Government Area of Benue State. *Psychology Reports*, 5(2), 1-7

Irish Journal of Educational Practice

Irish J. Edu Pract

Volume: 8; Issue: 06

November-December, 2025

ISSN: 2383 – 6345

Impact Factor: 5.46

Advance Scholars Publication
Published by International Institute of Advance
Scholars Development
<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/ijep>

Ode J., O., & Eriba, J., O. (2019). Teaching and learning of Basic Science in a recessed economy. *Education Rev. Lett.*,4(9), Pp 8.

Semali, L. M., & Kincheloe, J. L. (2022). *What is indigenous knowledge? Voices from the academy*. Routledge.

Verawati, N.N., Harjono, A., W ahyudi, A., & Gummah,S. (2022). Inquiry-creative learning integrated with ethnoscience: The efforts to encourage prospective science teacher's critical thinking in Indonesia. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 21(9), 232-248.